

Key Facts

Duration: October 2025 – September 2028

EU Contribution: € 5.999.865,72

Programme: Horizon Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: NETCOMPANY S.A. (Luxembourg)

Partners: A large, multidisciplinary consortium of 28 partners (including 2 associated plus 2 affiliated entities) from 10 European countries, bringing together technology providers, research centres, public authorities, emergency services, and infrastructure operators.

The Challenge

(Peri-)urban areas are becoming increasingly digital, interconnected, and complex. At the same time, threats such as climate change, natural disasters, and cyber-attacks are growing. This creates an urgent need to enhance the resilience and security of Critical Infrastructures (CIs) and the essential services they support. ECHO's primary objective is to create a multi-level Resilience Ecosystem that unites CI operators, Emergency Service Providers (ESPs), local/regional authorities, and emergency management professionals. Together, they will co-create innovative tools, services, and strategies for enhanced (urban) resilience planning and management.

The Mission

The project's mission is to empower stakeholders of all sizes to strengthen the resilience of interconnected systems, enhancing the security and wellbeing of European citizens and communities.

Its core approach is built on an EU-sovereign Knowledge Hub and a suite of interoperable, modular, and cost-effective services, accessible via a centralized Platform. Key features include:

- **Advanced Tools:** Threat forecasting, risk assessment, situational awareness, decision support, resilience plan evaluation, and scenario-based simulations.
- **Cutting-Edge Technology:** Using Generative AI for advanced modelling, forecasting, and decision-making while ensuring transparency and data security.
- **Information Sharing Protocol:** Enabling cost-effective resource pooling and collaboration, helping smaller municipalities overcome budget constraints.
- **Open Source & Open Data:** Leveraging open data, open models, and open-source software for transparency and wide adoption.

The Impact

The ECHO Knowledge Hub & Platform

- **Unified Resilience Ecosystem:** An EU-sovereign, modular platform offering cost-efficient services for multi-hazard resilience planning that aims to grow to 100+ experts and practitioners by the end of the project.
- **Tailored Multi-Hazard Tools:** Solutions addressing diverse threats including floods, landslides, drought, earthquakes, wildfires, infrastructure failures, and cyber-attacks.

Real-World Validation (4 Pilot Sites)

- **Pilot 1: Slovenia** – Addressing local hazards (e.g., floods, landslides).
- **Pilot 2: Italy** – Focusing on regional resilience challenges.
- **Pilot 3: Spain** – Testing solutions in the Andalusian context.
- **Pilot 4: Cross-border Italy-Slovenia** – Demonstrating coordinated cross-border resilience.

These pilots will actively engage diverse stakeholders (AUTs, ESPs, EMPs) to test and validate solutions in relevant settings, ensuring scalability and adaptability across Europe.

Capacity Building & Policy Impact

- **Best Practices & Guidelines:** Promoting best practices through comprehensive impact-generation activities.
- **Empowered Stakeholders:** Equipping smaller municipalities and resource-constrained organisations with affordable, collaborative resilience tools.
- **Contribution to EU Resilience:** Strengthening the security and resilience of European critical infrastructures and communities.